
A STUDY OF PERCEPTIONS OF B.ED. STUDENTS' ABOUT AI IN EDUCATION

Dr. Jitendra Subhash Shinde

Assistant Professor, Department of Education
Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Sub Campus Dharashiv

Abstract

Today, Artificial Intelligence- AI, Block chain, Multiverse etc. have changed all the activities related with Human life immensely. It is affecting on various chores of our life from human thinking processes to our teaching and learning, research and evaluation also. With these technological advancements, the machine learning in the form of artificial intelligence challenges human learning systems.

Related to this, NEP-2020 has also called to focus on teacher preparation with respect to application of AI in teaching and learning. In this regard, the researchers have made this attempt to explore the perceptions of B.Ed. students for applying AI in education.

For this study, the data has been collected from randomly selected 60 B.Ed. students from two local B.Ed. colleges through structured questionnaire consisted of forty questions based of AI tools and its application in education. The data has been analyzed on the basis of percentages.

The study revealed that most of B.Ed. students know about Chat-GPT for making notes and lesson plans and presentations, but they are not aware about many of the tools as well as its applicability for teaching, learning and evaluation of school students. They are also unaware about the use of AI in classroom setting for creating learning environment. This study concluded that there is prior need of AI based Teacher Preparation modules which can enhance the Quality and Accessibility of Education for all of us and avoid 'Digital Divide' in Education.

Key Words: AI, B.Ed. Students, NEP-2020 etc.

Introduction

After starting the NEP-2020 implementation in India, the role of technology has been massively increased and at the same time the machine learning and artificial intelligence has wide application with simple tools becomes possible for all of us. This makes most of our cognitive tasks easier and within time line. The use of artificial intelligence has been increased after 2020 pandemic, as our education system becomes online and in blended mode. Therefore, the teachers and students use different AI tools for teaching and learning respectively.

Connecting to the above situation, it is observed that most of us now use chat-GPT, Gemini and Seri which are easy to use for any purpose. AI gives readymade solutions for our queries regarding our problems and give output based on the given prompt. Actually it answered our queries based on the data available online. This feature of analyzing related data which is huge one and giving a solution for our query within a fraction of seconds makes AI very interesting and amazing.

By considering all these facts the researcher has made this attempt to explore the perceptions of B.Ed. students about AI in education and to suggest some AI tools for teaching, learning and evaluation to future teachers.

Need and Significance

The New Education Policy-2020 advocates use of ICT and AI to develop digital skills and online education platform for students of every level of education. It is observed that there is vast and huge number of researches taken place in different countries on AI and its application in various fields. These studies discussed the tools of AI for blended learning and assessment.

It is necessary to understand that the AI tools are useful to develop digital skills among students but it disrupts the natural learning styles of them. Here are some studies mentioned about application of AI in Education.

This research made an attempt to explore the perceptions of student teachers at B.Ed. level about AI in Education. It would be beneficial to develop a new teaching methodology based on AI tools which can be incorporated in Pre-service & In-service Teacher Education curriculum in India so as to develop teachers for new era of AI in Education.

Review of Literature:-

The researcher has reviewed literature on co-operative learning which has been given as follows.

Salvin, R. (1991) reported a complete synthesis of researches on co-operative learning by categorizing it as academic achievement, intergroup relations, mainstreaming, self-esteem and others. The co-operative learning approach has shown positive and significant results in academic achievement, intergroup relations among students, mainstreaming of the mentally or physically challenged students and self-esteem and self-concept of students. There are many researches based on application of co-operative learning for various subjects and students from various levels.

Co-operative Learning in Science:-

Lyons (1982), Yager (1985), Miller (1992), Ahuja (1995), Towns & Grant (1997) & Pande & Kishore (2001) reported greater efficiency of co-operative learning for science achievement over other traditional methods of teaching. Dheeraj & R. Kumari (2013) also reported similar findings for environmental science achievement.

Co-operative approach for Language Teaching:-

Gillies & Ashman (1998) reported that whenever students worked together on a learning task they show increased participation in interactions, engage in fewer interruptions when others speak and provide more intellectually valuable contribution in the form of their own views in their own words. Mohanty & Roy (2013) & Taun (2006) showed that students learned to use proper words & phrases while expressing their thoughts & feelings by following the principle of interdependence of co-operative learning.

Co-operative approach for Teachers & their Education:-

As this research related to future teacher educators, the researcher reviewed studies on Co-operative learning application in teacher education and attitude of teachers towards it. Hijazi & Al-Natour (2012) showed that the teachers' attitude towards co-operative learning was significantly different on the basis of their experience & educational level.

Agashe & Deshpande (2011) & Sohani, C. (2011) revealed from their studies that Co-operative approach is useful to develop linguistic abilities and conceptual understanding of student teachers as well as they gave positive feedback for co-operative learning methods.

Title of the study

A study of Perceptions of B.Ed. Students about AI in Education

Objectives

The objectives of the study were-

1. To explore the awareness of B.Ed. students regarding AI in Education.
2. To know perceptions of B.Ed. students regarding AI in Education.
3. To suggest measures for inculcating ethical use of AI Tools in Education.

Research Questions

Research questions posed for the study were-

1. What is the response of B.Ed. students to application of AI Tools in Education?
2. What are they perceive through co-operative approach in teaching?
3. What do they expect while dealing with co-operative approach in M.Ed. Classroom?

Methods and materials

Considering the qualitative nature of the study, the post-facto research method has been used. The purposively selected twenty-five students studying in M.Ed. were included in this study. They have been introduced with different co-operative learning methods and the M.Ed. subjects were taught by using co-operative structures. Then an experience sharing session has been organized in which all the students participated and were asked to share their experiences in co-operative learning sessions. They were asked to give their expectations regarding application of co-operative methods in teacher education. The data has collected by using an open ended questionnaire and analysed further.

Analysis and Interpretation

The descriptive data was recorded in the filled questionnaires by M.Ed. students based on their experiences and expectations about co-operative approach in teaching and learning in teacher education. The analysed data presented in the following tables.

Table 1. Experiences of M.Ed. students regarding Co-operative approach in Teacher Education

Sr. No.	Responses of students	Percentage
1	Firstly introduced with the co-operative approach	92.84
2	Makes us to think separately and individually	88.26
3	Helps to interact with each other	86.36
4	Expressing own thoughts	87.13
5	Acceptance for others thoughts	82.75
6	Group accountability and we feeling	84.44
7	Everyone participated and contributed	77.54
8	Enhances helping attitude and behaviour	74.87
9	Easy to implement and act on learning tasks	73.05
10	Group performance important	71.54
11	Develops rapport among students as well with teacher	69.58
12	Easiness in interaction	65.94
13	Understands concept dynamically	65.86
14	Helps to understand others perspective	63.59
15	Helps to make friends	58.36
16	Increases accountability for learning	58.28
17	Though feel slow but make me to think about others	57.47

From table 1, it is showed that the M.Ed. students understand the principles of co-operative approach through their own experiences. It also built a confidence about application of co-operative approach in their own presentations like seminars or model lessons.

The another part of study is related to know the expectations of M.Ed. students regarding co-operative approach in teacher education which is presented in table no. 2 as follows-

Table 2- Expectations of M.Ed. students regarding co-operative approach in Teacher Education

Sr. No.	Responses of students	Percentage
1	It should be part of teaching methodology	94.26
2	It should be included in D.El.Ed. & B.Ed. curriculum	92.54
3	Different co-operative structures should be introduced	91.22
4	The lesson should be based on co-operative approach	90.88
5	It should inculcate in practice teaching	90.64
6	There should be complete workshop on Co-operative approach	90.64
7	Teacher educators should trained regarding co-operative structures	90.34

From table 2, it is clear that the M.Ed. students expected that co-operative learning should be part of teacher education from primary level to tertiary level with a practical approach so as to prepare future teachers to implement co-operative approach in school education. They also insisted for including co-operative approach in preparation of teacher educators.

Findings and Discussion

The results showed that co-operative learning is useful for all levels of learning and students centred teaching. The student teachers did not know about the concept of co-operative approach and its' structures. The future teachers wanted to know the new methods based on innovative and newer approaches through teacher education courses. The results underlined importance of co-operative learning for better understanding of concepts as well as the better social skills among students by constructing co-operative environment in the classroom.

From the expectations of M.Ed. students it is understood that the teacher education curriculum in India should be redesigned and revamped according to the basic needs of today's school education. This should be helpful to develop required teaching skills based on different innovative approaches to education among future teachers and teacher educators.

Suggestions for implementation of Co-operative approach in Teacher Education

On the basis of findings the following suggestions has been given-

1. The teacher education must be a complete responsible structure from national to local level.
2. The new and innovative approaches should be part of teacher education curriculum.
3. The teachers' guide should be based on innovative approaches like co-operative and other.
4. There should short term courses based on each innovative practice for in-service teachers.
5. Teachers should be motivated new co-operative learning structures useful for Indian setting.
6. Separate researches should be done on different structures of co-operative learning in particular and other approaches in general.

Conclusion

The aim of education in India is to develop young generation with knowledge, attitude and civic sense and democratic values. For this, co-operative approach would be helpful to inculcate democratic values like equity, social justice and equal opportunities through co-operation at every level of education. For achieving this purpose, we have to introduce co-operative approach in our teacher education at primary, secondary and tertiary levels. It helps to build an education policy which works for every individual in India and makes him to learn co-operatively through co-operative approach. It makes every Indian to participate and contribute in each others' development through education. Due to this, we can achieve our dream evoked by Dr. A.P. J. Abdul Kalam to become India a 'Super Power' based on the principle of co-operation by the upcoming decade.

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